

KNOW-HOW AND METHODOLOGICAL GUIDANCE FOR PARENTS AND TEACHERS CONCERNING SOME OF THE MAIN FIELDS OF THE PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN DEVELOPMENT

Ardian Shingjergjiⁱ

Prof. Assoc. Dr. Faculty of Education Sciences,
"Aleksandër Xhuvani", University of Elbasan,
Albania

Abstract:

Child development is a lifelong process being associated with a series of specific changes which result to be more visible and vigorous in childhood. Achievements in technology with which the present-day children are being grown up as well as the advance of science have brought a challenging reality for parents, teachers and adults concerning quests and dilemmas they are being faced with in the course of their children's growth and development. In these terms, this study aims to convey some know-how and methodical guidance for both parents and teachers being involved with pre-school children education, mainly related to some of the main fields of the child's development. I think and hope that treated issues concerning pre-school children thorough development will serve as guidance and contribution to their healthy growing and education.

Keywords: children, pre-school, development, physic, motor, emotional, social

1. Introduction

Development is an all-round process of changes occurring to individuals during the whole course of their life. These changes are closely related to the process of the children's growing up, communication and move towards autonomy, assuming their role in society (Jareg, E.P.,1994), as well as with other features, qualities and skills serving as indicators in the main fields of development such as the cognitive, physical,

ⁱ Correspondence: email ardianshingjergji@gmail.com

motor, psycho-social and social domains. In these terms, teachers and parents should have a thorough knowledge of the phenomenon occurring in the course of this period of child's development in order to understand and affect as much as they can to the normal development of their children.

In order to make the evaluation of the pre-school children's development possible, the university pedagogues of education faculties as well as specialists of the child's early development should identify some of the peculiar features determining abilities which are achieved, more or less, at the same period of the children's lifetime which might serve as indicators of the main fields of child's growth.

Among principles leading to child's development, a very important one is the inclusive and independent principle, meaning that child's development has been simultaneously affected and affects all those s/he is in relation with. (Evans, J.L., Myers, R.G., Ilfeld, E.M., 2000)

However, it should always be kept in mind that every child is a unique individual and its development might be different from other children. This means that every child will develop in its own time and ways. As an argument for this assertion, it is enough to mention the fact that, generally babies walk at 12 months of their life but this does not mean that there are no children that began to walk when they are 11 or 13 months old. These variations should not, anyway, be confused with the disorders that can be displayed in the course of the child's development.

If teachers or parents notice that "something is going wrong" or that "the child is not developing properly", they should share their concerns with specialists, since, if deficiencies in their development are noticed early they can be treated successfully.

Children that have turned to three years old should not be considered babies any more. They are able to do greater things both physically and mentally. 3 – 6 years old children are developed slowly as compared to the previous lifetime period but they have an obvious progress in terms of their physical and mental development. Also, it is supposed that these years are the "golden years" of their development, even determining their personality.

Development in small children is realized in a cooperative and complementary way between different domains. In these terms, the progress of the child in a certain field affects his/her development in other fields as well. As an example, we can mention the fact that changes in the cognitive aspect affect the aspects of the linguistic and intellectual development as well as their increasing interest in the processes of learning, etc. Moreover, a child who learns to successfully pass over the narrow beam develops skills related to equilibrium, learns and evolves understanding the concept "narrow" as well as gains self-confidence which is a concept of emotional concept of development.

2. The physical and motor development

The child's physical and motor development includes, on its entirety, all the individual physical features, qualities and skills. In contrast to the preceding age, beginning from the age of three, children cease to be chubby, with noticeable evolvement of the abdominal muscles; instead, they form the normal body lines. Boys develop muscles whereas girls evolve fat tissues. During the 3 – 6 years old growth period, children get taller at an average of 4.5 – 7 cm a year and gain 2 – 3 kilograms of weight.

In terms of motor development children of this age make a visible progress in developing great motor skills, including running and jumping skills as well as fine motor skills suchlike buttoning and unbuttoning their clothes, copying figures, cutting with scissors, etc.

In general, children of this age are able to use their senses, (seeing, hearing, touching, smelling, testing, etc), to adjust their movements.

Also, the good physical health makes them capable of and gives them energy and stamina to actively participate in the learning process. So, per instance, once they learn to crawl or walk they grow their abilities to discover or look into things in the encircling ambience, which enhances their cognitive development.

Some of the main distinctive characteristics or features related to the aspects of the physical and motor development for 3 – 6 years old children are given in the following table;

Table 1: Characteristics of motor development of children aged 3-6 years

Development Fields	Age (3 – 4.5 yrs old)	Age (4.5 – 6 yrs old)
Great Motor Skills (Global)	Children of this age-group are able to keep balance of their body in running, move easily back and forth, walk over the beam whilst not shaking, catch and throw the ball and kick it as well as speed and slow their walking as needed. They can move their body and limbs after the music rhythm, can transport objects or things from one part of the gym to another, etc.	Later on, children improve motor abilities realizing more difficult activities. They can run fast and fall down rarely, can jump forward standing on one leg, can imitate by means of the position of their body and limbs, can combine some motor motions in an organized way, (twist around the body axis, jump on one or both legs, follow the music rhythm, etc.) avoid and jump over barriers whilst running, etc.)
Fine Motor Development	Children can catch the ball with both hands over the head and throw it away, turn the book pages one by one, button and unbutton their garments, keep the pencil with their thumb and forefinger,	Children can randomly use their hand in everyday activities, (keeping the spoon, the pencil etc.), catching the ball with one or both hands, keeping scissors with one hand and cutting modeled paper, can

	can draw by following models, turn the tap on and off, screw and unscrew bottle caps, brush teeth etc.	squeeze the glue and toothpaste tube, putting it where they like, putting on their shoes and fastening their laces, etc.
Sensory and Motor Development	Children imitate sounds of music instruments they hear, turn their eyes without turning their heads to see something, order sliding counters in the abacus, etc.	Children can draw figures with great accuracy and in details, make constructions with various materials, by using their imagination or fantasy, etc.

3. The Children’s Psycho-Emotional and Social Development

Psycho-Emotional Development includes the general development of individual’s senses, emotions and desires in relevance to himself and the others. The social development involves exploring and understanding ways of individual’s behavior in rapport with the society. It stands on the foundation of all development since all the information obtained by children comes from the attached figures serving as a vivid reflection in the first years of their life. (Horno, P., 2005).

At this age, social-emotional development of children is affected by the parents, sisters and brothers’ behavior as well as the behavior of the adults in general. To this point, we should bear in mind that parents or teachers behave in different ways to them. A well balanced behavior is characterized by a stable emotional relationship of open understanding and communication between children and adults. On the contrary, retributive behaviors of parents, teachers or adults to children make the latter to grow up with the feeling of dependency from others, devoid of their own initiatives.

That is why parents, teachers and the adults in general should give children the possibility to actively participate in various activities helping them to be able to act by themselves, to direct children by helping them to adjust with the rules of the society. By nature, people are social beings. Pre-school age is the one when children create their first social links with their coevals; they are given possibilities to express their emotions, show understanding, help and respect others as well as understanding the need for individual freedom and independence. Social dexterities and emotional development are important part of the children’s bringing up by parents and teachers.

Table 2: Characteristics of the emotional and social development of children aged 3-6 years

Fields of Development	Age 3 – 4.5 years old	Age 4.5 – 6 years old.
Emotional Development	Children of this age-group get excited when they get presents, try to comfort another child when s/he cries, asks him/her “why s/he is crying”, answers to such questions as “Can you sing?”, “Can you turn the TV off?” “Can you draw” in a positive way. Children of this age group tell proudly what they can do to adults and react by their mimic when they are sad.	Children of this age-group are able to convey information for themselves and the others, (name, surname, location etc), can express emotions through playing, can control and refrain from negative and momentum emotions, (quickly interrupts feelings of sadness, discontent) and collaborate with the group, respect rules, are proud for their achievements and believe in their abilities.
Social Development	Children of this age-group divide toys and things with coevals, play with the adults, ask for help to familiar individuals, pay attention to their apparel in alien ambiances, try to resemble to someone, queue when they ask for something, raise their hands when addressing to the teacher, etc.	Children greet acquaintances when they meet them, they are able to notice similarities and distinctions in people, ask questions related to other children or newcomers, about any of their distinctive features, families, cultural distinctions, names familiar faces in photos, on television, makes friends in various ambiances, (home, kindergarten), plays and collaborates with new friends and groups.

4. Conclusions

- Childhood is an important phase in people’s life so it is significant that adults, parents and teachers should understand the values of this phase of life and the child’s development.
- Development is a long-term, inclusive and multidimensional process characterized by a series of changes in which children begin to evolve even more complicated levels of motions, thinking, sensing and interacting with other people and objects of the surrounding ambiance.
- Adults, parents and teachers should know the main fields of child’s development better and follow education specialists’ suggestions or advice scrupulously, so that children have been offered the best chances to be active social actors and potential contributors to the society.

Bibliography

1. Bojaxhi, A. "Parents - child's first and lifelong teachers". (2004). Toena. Tiranë.
2. Baranowski, T., Davis, M., et al. "Health Education and Behavior". (2000), 27(1): 96-111.
3. Berk, L. "Child Development", (2000), 5-th Edition, Allyn& Bacon.Boston.
4. Damovska, L., Ministerstvozatrudisocialna. "Standards for 0 – 6 years old child's early teaching and development". (2009). Translated into Albanian by Deari, A. Skopje.
5. Evans, J.L., Myers, R.G., Ilfeld, E.M. "Early childhood counts: A Programming guide over the care for the Early Childhood Development" (2000). Banka Botërore. Washington DC.
6. Jareg, E.P. "Working with children through dialogue". (1994). Redd BarnaPb.Mc.Millan.
7. Horno, P. "Love, Power and Violence: An intercultural comparison of the physical and psychological punishment" (2005). Save the Children. Spain.
8. Hammer, T., Turnover, P. "Parenting in Contemporary Society". (1990). Prentice-Hall Inc. USA.
9. Tahsini, I. "Models and Wonts of working with children" (2004). Tiranë.
10. http://kidshealth.org/parent/positivefamily/net_safety.html
11. <http://preschoolers.about.com/od/learningeducation/al/PreKpreleson.htm>
12. www.child-development-guide
13. www.parents.com
14. www.kidsgrowth.com

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).